

Application of Reinforcement Learning for EVs Charging Management in Low-Voltage Grids: A Case of Voltage Regulation

Sajjad Fattaheian-Dehkordi

Department of Electrical Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland

Gil Silva Sampaio

Power and Energy Systems Center
INESC TEC Institute
Porto, Portugal

Matti Lehtonen

Department of Electrical Engineering
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland

Abstract—The rapid proliferation of uncontrolled resources poses significant voltage regulation challenges in low-voltage (LV) distribution grids. In this condition, conventional charging strategies, often based on fixed or static schedules, may lead to adverse voltage deviations under unpredictable load conditions and variable renewable generation. To address these challenges, this paper studies a hybrid deep reinforcement learning (DRL) framework based on a Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) policy network enriched by a Graph Convolution Variation (GCV) feature extractor to improve voltage regulation issues in LV grids. In addition to ensuring that electric vehicles (EVs) achieve their required state-of-charge (SoC), the framework dynamically adjusts charging rates in real time to maintain LV-grid voltage within acceptable limits. Extensive simulation results, including detailed analysis and comparisons with the static charging method, demonstrate significant improvements in voltage regulation, and enhanced overall grid performance. The obtained results demonstrate the effectiveness of controlling EVs' charging controls in an intelligent manner to address the voltage regulation issue in low-voltage grids.

Index Terms—Electric Vehicles, Voltage Regulation, Low-Voltage Grid, DRL, PPO, Graph Neural Network, GCV, Reinforcement learning.

NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
EV	Electric Vehicle
GCV	Graph Convolution Variation
LV	Low-Voltage
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MSE	Mean Squared Error
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization
PV	Photovoltaic
SoC	State of Charge

Sets and Index

N	Total number of nodes in the grid
i	Node index ($i = 1, \dots, N$)

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t	Time step or hour of operation
ϵ	Clipping parameter in PPO
$\mathcal{N}(i)$	Set of neighbors of node i
$[0, T]$	Time horizon for an episode
Parameters	
C_{\max}	Maximum charging level
V_0	Slack bus voltage (set to 1.0 p.u.)
R_{ij}	Resistance of the line between nodes i and j
X_{ij}	Reactance of the line between nodes i and j
$P_{\text{net}}(i, t)$	Net power at node i at time t
$PV(i, t)$	PV generation at node i at time t
$\text{Load}(i, t)$	Load at node i at time t
$P_i^{\text{EV}}(t)$	EV charging power at node i at time t
V_i	Voltage at node i
$E_{\text{req}}(i)$	Total energy requirement for the EV at node i
$E_{\text{delivered}}(i)$	Energy delivered to the EV at node i
$t_{\text{arr}}, t_{\text{dep}}$	EV arrival and departure times
$\Delta_{i,t}$	Action: adjustment to the baseline charging rate at node i and time t
r_t	Reward at time t
θ	Policy network parameters
$\pi_{\theta}(a_t s_t)$	Probability of taking action a_t in state s_t under policy θ
\hat{A}_t	Advantage estimate

I. INTRODUCTION

The rising adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) has altered traditional power consumption patterns in low-voltage (LV) distribution grids. Unlike predictable household loads, EV charging demands can increase unexpectedly, leading to severe local voltage drops. As EV penetration continues to grow, these effects may worsen, compromising both reliability and power quality. At the same time, modern distribution grids increasingly incorporate distributed energy resources such as rooftop photovoltaics (PV) [1], which will add variability to the net load of the grid and pose critical challenges in the voltage regulation process in LV-grids. Therefore, novel management techniques should be applied to control the local flexible resources, such as EVs in LV grids, to address the potential voltage regulation issues in the grid.

Recent research shows that methods such as reinforcement learning (RL) offer an adaptive alternative by enabling an intelligent agent to learn from ongoing interactions with the environment to operate power resources. Chen et al. in [2] provide a comprehensive review of RL applications across various power system problems, including frequency regulation, voltage control, and energy management. The paper proposes a roadmap for future research and highlight the transformative potential of RL in modern power system control. A deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based home energy management system is developed in [3] that optimizes the scheduling of household appliances, energy storage, and EV charging. The proposed system considers both customer comfort and the loading conditions of distribution transformers. Simulation results demonstrate that the DRL agent can effectively reduce electricity costs and improve transformer load profiles. Reference [4] proposes a DRL framework that formulates microgrid management as a sequential decision-making problem under uncertainty. This approach extracts temporal features from past consumption and PV production data to activate flexible energy sources (e.g., short-term batteries and long-term storage systems) effectively. This work highlights the potential of DRL in handling stochastic renewable generation and load uncertainties. Alfaverh et al. in [5] utilized RL for EV integration in demand response programs, emphasizing the benefits of vehicle-to-grid and vehicle-to-home technologies. This study illustrates that EVs, when managed intelligently, can serve as both flexible loads and distributed energy storage resources that support grid stability. Moreover, the investigation conducted in [6] shows that RL-based controllers can maintain voltage levels more accurately than traditional optimization methods. Furthermore, authors in [7] explore the application of supervised learning for operating low-voltage grids. This study demonstrates how a neural network model can integrate off-line regression predictions with real-time control of AC/DC converters. The findings suggest that machine learning offers promising solutions for future grid operation.

A decentralized energy management system is developed in [8] to optimize EV charging in islanded microgrids. The proposed system not only reduces investment costs but also increases the number of chargeable EVs while mitigating peak loads and load variances. Moreover, [9] formulates the EV charging and discharging as a sequential decision-making problem to minimize individual user charging costs by maximizing the effective use of EV batteries. In [10], EV charging and discharging process is optimized with other flexible resources to address the real-time energy imbalance in local energy systems. The approach developed in [11] integrates demand response (DR) pricing with voltage control through a multi-agent RL framework. This approach manages both household energy consumption and voltage violations. The results show the effectiveness of multi-agent cooperation in grid control. Reference [12] addresses the dual challenges of enhancing system resilience and reducing carbon intensity by leveraging EV flexibility. Their hybrid multiagent RL framework computes both discrete routing and continuous scheduling actions for EVs in a coupled power-transportation network. Simulation results demonstrate improved resilience under extreme events and highlight the role of EVs in supporting a low-carbon future. A real-time home energy management system is designed in [13] that balances active

and reactive power to improve the home-to-grid power factor and reduce electricity bills. This work underscores the benefits of applying DRL in residential energy management.

Based on the above discussions, this paper focuses on developing a DRL framework to manage the charging of EVs in an LV-grid while improving voltage regulation in the system. On the other hand, as ignoring the grid's topology or relying solely on node-level data can limit DRL's capability to preserve voltage regulation across a radial network, Graph Convolution Variation (GCV) is applied to address this limitation by embedding line impedances and connectivity information into the agent's perception, thereby enabling improved node-to-node coordination.

In this paper, Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) is selected as the DRL backbone for its stable updates. By clipping the policy's probability ratio, PPO prevents excessively large steps that might destabilize the learned policy. Integrated with GCV, this approach manages EV charging at each node to maintain voltages within the range of [0.9–1.1] p.u. while meeting EV users energy demands.

The contributions are

- Developing a hybrid DRL mechanism that merges a forward-backward sweep load flow with GCV-based state extraction method to address the grid topology.
- Modeling a PPO agent that handles real-time node-level adjustments, ensuring improved voltage regulation while meeting the EV users energy demand.

In this regard, simulation tests over training and validation scenarios confirm substantial improvements in voltage regulation compared to static charging of EVs. Section II presents the background and problem statement. Section III details the developed methodology, including radial grid modeling and static baseline scheduling. Moreover, PPO and GCV models are described in this section. In Section IV, the integrated algorithm is described, and Section V highlights the case studies and obtained results. Section VI presents the conclusion of the paper.

II. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

LV distribution networks often feature radial topologies, limited fault levels, and relatively small conductor sizes. As more EVs converge during certain hours (e.g., evenings), voltage drops may reach unacceptable levels without dynamic control. Meanwhile, rooftop PV installations can cause reverse power flows, occasionally causing over-voltage in the grid.

Balancing EV user satisfaction (i.e., charging to the desired state of charge (SoC)) and grid constraints becomes a multi-objective challenge. Traditional day-ahead optimization requires accurate forecasts and may lack real-time adaptability. In contrast, reinforcement learning can respond promptly to evolving load conditions through trial-and-error corrections, guided by a power flow solver that computes the actual node voltages.

Thus, the core problem that will be addressed in this paper is:

- 1) **Voltage Control:** Improving voltage regulation to be stated within standard operational limits which are considered to be [0.9, 1.1] p.u..
- 2) **Energy Fulfillment:** Ensure that each EV meets its SoC target during the charging period.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodologies applied for operating the grid, and developing the DRL-based EV management algorithm. In this regard, the radial distribution model, the forward-backward sweep solver, the baseline EV charging approach, Markov Decision Process (MDP) as well as PPO and GCV for real-time decisions are presented in the following sub-sections.

A. Radial LV Grid Model

Consider an LV feeder with N nodes indexed by $i = 1, \dots, N$ and a substation slack at $i = 0$ with $V_0 = 1.0$ p.u. Each line (i, j) has an impedance defined as $z_{ij} = R_{ij} + jX_{ij}$. At time t , the net power at node i is given by:

$$P_{\text{net}}(i, t) = \text{PV}(i, t) - \left[\text{Load}(i, t) + P_i^{\text{EV}}(t) \right] \quad (1)$$

The forward-backward sweep is performed as follows:

- **Backward Pass:** Initialize currents $I_i = 0$ for all i . For each node i , compute $I_i = \overline{S}_i / \overline{V}_i$ and accumulate its current with the children nodes to determine the current between node i and its parent node.
- **Forward Pass:** Starting from V_0 , calculates voltages downstream using $V_j = V_i - z_{ij} \cdot I_j$. This process will be repeated until changes fall below a specified tolerance.

This method accurately calculates the voltage levels of radial LV systems. In real time operation of the grid, aside PV and load demands, EVs power charging could impact the voltage regulation of the grid, which will be optimized by the RL agent.

B. Baseline EV Charging

Assume that each EV at node i requires a total energy $E_{\text{req}}(i)$ over an interval $[t_{\text{arr}}, t_{\text{dep}}]$. A naive baseline called the static charging process divides the required energy evenly over the available time as follows:

$$\text{Base}_{i,t} = \min \left(C_{\text{max}}, \frac{E_{\text{req}}(i) - E_{\text{delivered}}(i)}{t_{\text{dep}} - t} \right) \quad (2)$$

This methodology assumes that each EV could be charged based on the baseline EV charging to meet the required energy by the user. It is noteworthy that an intelligent management technique run by an RL agent could modify these baseline charging rates in real-time operation to effectively manage the grid voltage regulation. Therefore, the following sections will discuss the structure of the algorithm for developing an RL agent to control the EVs charging in the system.

C. Markov Decision Process (MDP)

In the developed framework, we discretize time into steps $t = 1, \dots, T$. The MDP elements are defined as:

- **State s_t :** Includes node voltages, SoCs, baseline schedules, net load, and GCV embeddings.
- **Action a_t :** An array $\Delta_{i,t}$ that adjusts the baseline from $\text{Base}_{i,t}$ to $\text{Base}_{i,t} + \Delta_{i,t}$, with values clamped to $[0, C_{\text{max}}]$.
- **Reward r_t :** The negative sum of voltage violation penalties plus penalties for failing to meet EV SoC requirements by departure.
- **Transition:** The environment updates node voltages via the forward-backward sweep and calculates the next state s_{t+1} .

These components feed into the DRL training loop, where the agent learns to minimize voltage deviations while fulfilling EV demands.

D. Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

PPO is a policy gradient method known for balancing sample efficiency with stable learning. After collecting trajectories over multiple time steps, it updates the actor parameters θ by maximizing the clipped objective as below:

$$L^{\text{clip}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E} \left[\min(r_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1-\epsilon, 1+\epsilon) \hat{A}_t) \right] \quad (3)$$

where

$$r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t | s_t)} \quad (4)$$

Moreover, \hat{A}_t presents the advantage estimate. Clipping ensures that $r_t(\theta)$ does not deviate too far from 1, thus preventing excessively large policy updates.

E. Graph Convolution Variation (GCV) with Forecast Compression

To effectively capture the grid topology and temporal forecast information, we integrate a graph-based feature extractor that combines graph convolution with a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) for forecast compression.

1) **Graph Convolution for Node Embeddings:** Node-level features—including instantaneous load, PV generation, connection status, remaining energy fraction, baseline charging rate, grid depth, and electrical distance—are arranged into feature vectors. Finally, graph convolution layers aggregate these features across neighboring nodes based on the grid's connectivity.

2) **Forecast Compression via MLP:** A high-dimensional forecast vector, which comprises future load, PV profiles, and EV baseline forecasts over a fixed horizon, is compressed using an MLP. The MLP reduces the dimensionality from the original forecast space, capturing important temporal trends.

3) **Feature Concatenation:** The compressed forecast features and the global graph embedding are concatenated and passed through a final fully connected layer to generate the final state representation. This enriched representation is provided as input to the PPO policy network, allowing for more informed decision-making in EV charging management.

IV. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Based on the discussions in the previous section, the developed stepwise procedure for training the RL agent and optimizing the PPO policy is as follows:

- 1) **Baseline:** The EV obtains an initial schedule by evenly distributing the required energy over the available charging window.
- 2) **GCV Embeddings:** Node features (voltage, SoC, depth, adjacency) are transformed into embeddings.
- 3) **RL Action:** The PPO agent outputs a node-wise correction $\Delta_{i,t}$ to each baseline rate.
- 4) **Voltage Update:** With the updated net power, the forward-backward sweep re-calculates the nodal voltages.
- 5) **Reward:** Penalties for voltage deviations and SoC shortfalls are aggregated to form the reward.
- 6) **Policy Improvement:** The PPO agent updates the actor-critic networks using the collected samples.

Note that Figure 1 illustrates how the forward-backward sweep, GCV, PPO, and computed reward function will form the training framework.

Fig. 1. Simplified model of the developed process

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

In this section, a more detailed description about implementing the developed PPO+GCV framework as well as the obtained results are discussed. In this regard, the main points of the implemented model are as below:

- 1) **Scenario Pool:** A pool of 5000 scenarios is pre-generated, each with daily load/PV profiles and EV schedules. The EV schedules are adapted from the local EV charging dataset at INESC-TEC.
- 2) **Environment:** The environment utilizes the forward-backward sweep method for voltage calculations, baseline scheduling updates, and reward shaping via voltage and SoC penalties. The model of the test system considered for the LV grid is shown in Figure 2.
- 3) **Feature Extractor:** A multi-layer graph convolutional network (GCN-Conv) is embedded within the policy network processes node-level features, including load, PV, baseline rate, and depth.
- 4) **PPO Hyperparameter Tuning:** We leverage optuna for hyperparameter search (learning rate, entropy coefficient, etc.) and retrain using the best-found parameters.

Fig. 2. Configuration of the LV test grid.

A. Observations

1) Training Reward Progression

Figures 3 and 4 show the improvement in the mean value of the training reward and Mean Squared Error (MSE) of the voltage over 1 million time steps. In this paper, the voltage MSE measures the total square root of the nodal

voltage deviations above or below the permissible bounds ($[0.9, 1.1]$ p.u.) in the grid. Moreover, The total reward shows the aggregated 24-hour reward, incorporating both voltage and SoC penalties. Note that each training step includes 24 time steps of a day as each scenario in the pool includes one day scheduling. Obtained results show that the policy converges steadily, indicating stable learning. Beyond 75000 training steps, the reward saturates, suggesting that the agent consistently finds near-optimal charging strategies.

Fig. 3. Evaluation of mean reward during training.

Fig. 4. Evaluation of mean voltage MSE during training.

2) Scenario specific Analysis

As discussed before, during evening and night peak loads, the baseline EV charging strategy can lead to voltage dips below 0.9 p.u. in the grid. In other words, due to high load demands during evening and night, the grid could confront with under voltage issue and concurrent charging of EVs could exacerbate this condition. On the other hand, during the mid-day, the over power generation by PV units could result in over-voltage in the grid. As a result, the RL agent learns that revising the EV charging plans could decrease the voltages above 1.1 p.u. In this regard, this sub-section discusses the behavior of RL agent and its impact on the voltage of different nodes in the grid for Scenario 2 selected from the pool. Figure 5 show the voltage in different nodes of the grid for RL agent and base case (i.e. baseline EV charging). The results show that the RL solution effectively mitigates undervoltage and overvoltage conditions by reducing or shifting charging loads. Furthermore, Figures 6 compares the baseline and RL charging profiles of EVs at each node. The RL policy selectively shifts charging (depending on local voltage conditions) to improve voltage regulation while still meeting the EV demands by departure time. This pattern shows the tendency of shifting the EVs charging to mid-day to also address the over-voltage condition in the grid. Moreover, hourly rewards are plotted to highlight differences in penalty over a 24-hour span. A higher reward indicates more stable voltages and better fulfillment of EV demands.

Figure 7 shows how the baseline strategy results in higher penalties in the hours when voltage constraints are violated.

Fig. 5. Voltage of the LV grid in case of baseline charging vs RL control in the considered scenario.

Fig. 6. Detailed node-level comparison of EV power charging in baseline and RL control over 24 hours in the considered scenario.

In contrast, the RL approach moderates charging during peak load intervals and reduces penalties, leading to higher net rewards.

3) Statistical Results Over Scenario Pool

In order to show the effectiveness of the developed RL-based method for charging management of EVs to improve the voltage regulation in an LV grid, here, the *Mean Voltage MSE* and *Mean Total Reward* are evaluated over the scenario pool. In this regard, Figure 8 shows that the RL approach significantly reduces the mean voltage MSE compared to the baseline charging of the EVs. On the other hand, Figure 9 indicates significantly improved total rewards, implying fewer voltage violations and more successful SoC fulfillment while applying the RL approach.

Fig. 7. Hourly reward for the baseline and RL agent in the considered scenario.

Fig. 8. Mean MSE voltage over the scenario pool.

Fig. 9. Mean reward over the scenario pool.

5) Analyzing Validation Scenarios

To verify generalization, the trained policy is tested on 100 new scenarios generated aside from the scenario pool. The obtained results are shown in Figure 10 and 11. The results show that the RL approach consistently outperforms the baseline EV charging, reinforcing that the learned policy could effectively optimize the EV charging to improve the voltage regulations in the LV grid.

Fig. 10. Comparison of total reward (RL vs baseline) for validation scenarios.

Fig. 11. Comparison of voltage MSE (RL vs baseline) for validation scenarios.

Overall, the obtained results in simulations show the robustness of the proposed GCV-RL scheme, demonstrat-

ing consistent voltage regulation benefits, flexible handling of high PV penetration, and stable generalization to new scenarios.- This improvement is mainly due to the agent's ability to consider more than a single node's SoC demands and to coordinate charging among multiple nodes via GCV embeddings.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a comprehensive DRL-based method for EV charging management in IV grids by coupling PPO with a GCV to exploit grid structure dependencies. The forward-backward sweep load flow ensures accurate voltage modeling at each time step, while EV baseline schedules provide a feasible default charging strategy. This approach outperforms static baselines by dynamically re-allocating charging power to maintain voltages within operational limits. Noted that despite shifting charging for voltage regulation, the RL strategy ensures that EVs reach at their requested SoC by departure. In other words, only in extremely congested scenarios, the policy may have to apply trade-offs. The extended implementation and experimental results across the scenario pool and validation scenarios confirm the robustness of the proposed technique.

Future work will focus on extending multi-agent coordination across multiple feeders and incorporating dynamic pricing signals for advanced EV charging management.

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